

On some Synthetic Compounds related to Atophan.

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2-Phenylquinoline-4-carboxylic acid (I, known under the trade name of 'Atophan' and 'Cinchophen') is a valuable synthetic drug. It possesses antipyretic as also antiphlogistic action, but the most important physiological property of the drug is the uricosuric action and hence its administration in the treatment of gout or rheumatism. It is, however, not a harmless substance as is generally supposed and indiscriminate use, even in clinical doses, has resulted in many fatal accidents, the victims developing gastro-intestinal disturbances and jaundice sooner or later. Attempts have been made to modify the structure of atophan with a view to diminish its undesirable pathological reactions on the liver, but satisfactory results have so far not been obtained. The modified atophans may be classified as follows :

- (i) Esters of atophan.
- (ii) Atophan derivatives having substituents in the phenyl nucleus in position 2.
- (iii) Atophan derivatives having substituents in the benzene nucleus of the quinoline ring.

A study of the chemical constitution and uricosuric action of these and allied compounds shows that a phenyl group in position-2 and a carboxyl group in position 4 of the quinoline nucleus are essential for the uricosuric action. Substituents [such as OH, Me, OMe, Ph, CO₂H, -O-CH₂-O-, As: O(OH)₂] attached to the phenyl group or the pyridine ring do not improve the quality of the drug, but have on the contrary often harmful effects (Niccolai, *Deut. Arch. klin. Med.*, 1908, **93**, 331; Dohrn, *Munch. med. Wochenschr.*, 1912, **59**, 568; *Biochem. Z.*, 1912, **43**, 240; *Z. klin. Med.*, 1912, **74**, 444; Impens, *Arch. intern. Pharmakodyn.*, 1912, **22**, 379). Introduction of substituents in the benzene nucleus has no harmful effect but it often, though not always, reduces or suppresses the uricosuric action. Similar results are obtained when the CO₂H group of atophan is esterified or converted into an amide.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to prepare compounds of the type (II) and study their physiological action. An inspection of the formula shows that it satisfies the two funda-

mental conditions necessary for uricosuric action, namely a phenyl group in position 2 and a carboxyl in position 4. Moreover, interposed between the phenyl and the quinoline nuclei there is a furan ring which is likely to influence the physiological activity of the compounds. The substances have been prepared by condensing isatin

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

with relevant coumaranones in alkaline medium. Incidentally the compounds III—V have been prepared from isatin on the one hand and β -anisoylpropionic acid, α -naphthylmethylketone and β -naphthylmethylketone on the other. The physiological action of these complex furoquinolines will be investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Coumaranones.—Coumaranones were prepared by Mameli's method (*Gazzetta*, 1926, **56**, 759) which was found to give better yields than the methods of Störmer and Bartsch (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 3177) or Störmer and Atenstadt (*Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3569).

Methylcoumaranones were prepared by the method of Higginbotham and Stephen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1534) and 6-oxycoumaranone by the method of Arima and Okamoto (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1929, 80, 344).

Condensation of Coumaranones with Isatic Acid.—One mol. of isatin was boiled with an excess of alcoholic potassium hydroxide for 20 mins. One mol. of coumaranone was then added and the mixture kept at about 70° for 3—4 hours. The solution was then made just acidic with dilute hydrochloric acid and the yellow precipitate collected. The acids were purified through the sodium salts. For this purpose the acids were dissolved in dilute sodium carbonate solution avoiding excess, charcoaled and filtered and the filtrate concentrated. The sodium salts were collected and decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with water, alcohol and finally with acetone. The yields were generally good. The compounds formed cream-coloured microcrystalline substances, sparingly soluble in acids but easily in sodium bicarbonate solutions. Condensations with β -anisoylpropionic acid and the naphthylmethylketones were similarly carried out. The following table summarises the analytical and other data of the compounds.

Compounds.	M. p.	Yield.	Analytical data.	
			Found.	Calc.
2:3-Benzofuroquinoline-4-carboxylic acid, $C_{16}H_9O_3N$, from coumaranone (II)	277°	81%	C, 72.68 % 72.68 H, 3.09 3.49 N, 5.44	73.00% 3.42 5.32
Sodium salt, $C_{16}H_8O_3NNa$.	—	—	Na, 7.91	8.07
2:3-(12-Methyl) benzofuroquinoline-4-carboxylic acid, $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N$, from 7-methylcoumaranone.	286°	64	C, 73.53 H, 4.22	73.64 3.97
Sodium salt $C_{17}H_{10}O_3NNa, 2H_2O$.	—	—	Na, 6.76 H_2O , 10.74	6.87 10.75
2:3-(11-Methyl) benzofuroquinoline-4-carboxylic acid, $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N$, from 6-methylcoumaranone	281°	80	C, 73.18 H, 4.17 N, 4.86	73.64 3.97 5.05
Sodium salt, $C_{17}H_{10}O_3NNa$.	—	—	Na, 7.45	7.69

SYNTHETIC COMPOUNDS RELATED TO ATOPHAN 703

Compounds.	M.p.	Yield.	Analytical data.	
			Found.	Calc.
2 : 3 - (10-Methyl-) benzofuro-quinoline-4-carboxylic acid, $C_{17}H_{11}O_3N$ from 5-methyl-coumaranone.	275°	50%	C, 73.52% H, 4.11	73.64% 3.97
2 : 3-(11-Hydroxy-) benzofuro-quinoline-4-carboxylic acid, $C_{16}H_9O_4N$, from 6-hydroxy-coumaranone.	309°	70	C, 68.74, 68.79 H, 3.46, 3.44 N, 4.93	68.82 3.23 5.02
2 - <i>p</i> -Anisylquinoline-4-carboxylic - 3 - acetic acid (III), $C_{19}H_{15}O_5N$ from $MeO \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2H$.	273° (reddish at 210°)	66	C, 67.61 H, 4.55 N, 3.86	67.66 4.45 4.16
2 - α -Naphthylquinoline-4-carboxylic acid (IV), $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$, from methyl- α -naphthyl-ketone.	195-97°	79	C, 79.87 H, 4.50 N, 4.54	80.26 4.35 4.68
2 - β -Naphthylquinoline -4-carboxylic acid (V), $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$, from methyl- β -naphthyl ketone.	248°	90	C, 79.91 H, 4.65 N, 4.62	80.26 4.35 4.68
Sodium salt, $C_{20}H_{12}O_2NNa$	—	—	Na, 7.06	7.16

* All the C-H estimations were carried out by ter Meulen's semi-micro method. Samples were dried at 110° in vacuum before analysis.

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